

Hateful Speech in Online College Communities

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ABSTRACT

Background. Hateful speech bears negative repercussions and is particularly damaging in college communities. The efforts to regulate hateful speech on college campuses pose vexing socio-political problems, and the interventions to mitigate the effects require evaluating the pervasiveness of the phenomenon on campuses as well as the impacts on students' psychological state.

Data and Methods. Given the growing use of social media among college students, we target the above issues by studying the online aspect of hateful speech in a dataset of 6 million Reddit comments shared in 174 college communities. We devise a measure of College Hate Index (CHX) and examine its distribution in college subreddits across the categories of hateful speech, *behavior*, *class*, *disability*, *ethnicity*, *gender*, *physical appearance*, *race*, *religion*, and *sexual orientation*. We then employ a causal-inference framework to study the psychological effects of hateful speech in these college subreddits, particularly in the form of individuals' online stress expression. Finally, we characterize their psychological endurance to hateful speech by analyzing their language— we examine their discriminatory keyword use with Sparse Additive Generative Model (SAGE), and their personality traits with Watson Personality Insights API.

Results. Our findings suggest that hateful speech is prevalent in college subreddits, and 25% of these subreddits show greater hateful speech than non-college subreddits. We further find that exposure to hate leads to greater stress expression. However, everybody exposed is not equally affected; some show lower psychological endurance than others. Low endurance individuals are more vulnerable to emotional outbursts, and are more neurotic than those with higher endurance to hate.

Discussion. Our work bears implications for policy-making and intervention efforts to tackle the damaging effects of online hateful speech in colleges. From technological perspective, our work caters to mental health support provisions on college campuses, and to moderation efforts in online college communities. In addition, given the charged aspect of speech dilemma, we highlight the ethical implications of our work. Our work lays the foundation for studying the psychological impacts of hateful speech in online communities in general, and situated communities in particular (the ones that have both an offline and an online analog).

KEYWORDS

social media; Reddit; hateful speech; mental health; stress; natural language analysis; college subreddits

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1 INTRODUCTION

Colleges are places where intellectual debate is considered as a key aspect of the educational pursuit, and where viewpoint diversity is venerated. Many colleges in the U.S. have been homes of the free speech movement of the 1960s, that catalyzed positive outcomes, ranging from the women's suffrage movement to the civil rights protests [24]. However, the last few decades has also witnessed several instances where minority groups in colleges have been targeted with verbal altercations, slander, defamation, and hateful speech [9]. In fact, between 2015 and 2016, there has been a 25%¹ rise in the number of reported hate crimes on college campuses.

Because colleges are close-knit, diverse, and geographically situated communities of students, the harmful effects of hateful speech are manifold. In addition to being a precursor to potential hate crimes and violence, hateful speech and its exposure can have profound psychological impacts on a campus's reputation, climate, and morale, such as heightened stress, anxiety, depression, and desensitization [15, 33]. Victimization, direct or indirect, has also been associated with increased rates of alcohol and drug use [30]—behaviors often considered risky in the formative college years [22]. Further, hateful speech exposure has negative effects on students' academic lives and performance, with lowered self-esteem, and poorer task quality and goal clarity—disrupting the very educational and vocational foundations that underscore college experience [5, 18].

Given the pervasive adoption of social media technologies in the college student population [23] and as students increasingly appropriate these platforms for academic, personal and social life discussions [1], hateful speech has begun to manifest online as well [6]. This adds a new dimension to the existing issues surrounding college speech. For instance, it has been reported to be a key driver of and an exacerbating factor behind harassment, bullying, and other violent incidents targeting vulnerable students, often making people feel unwelcome in both digital and physical spaces [11, 30], and even causing psychological and emotional upheavals, akin to its offline counterpart [20, 32].

Campus administrators and other stakeholders have therefore been reported to have struggled with mitigating the negative effects of online hateful speech on campuses, while at the same time valuing students' First Amendment rights [2, 12]. An important step towards addressing existing challenges is to first assess the pervasiveness of online hateful speech, and the vulnerability, in terms of psychological well-being, it presents to marginalized communities on college campuses. However, currently methods to make these assessments are heavily limited. Most existing reports are anecdotal,

¹[chronicle.com/article/After-2016-Election-Campus/242577](https://www.chronicle.com/article/After-2016-Election-Campus/242577)

Figure 1: (a) Distribution of category-specific CHX; (b) Histogram of category-aggregated CHX over college subreddits; (c) Kernel Density Estimation of hate lexicon’s absolute log-likelihood ratio (LLR) distribution in banned (bn.) against college (clg.) and non-college (alt.) subreddits.

that have been covered in popular media outlets [14], and are based on discrete events. At the same time, there is no empirical way to comprehensively and proactively quantify and characterize the hateful speech that surface online in the student communities. In addition, social confounds such as the stigma of being exposed to, and the psychological ramifications of hate often lead to underestimates of the effects of online hate, further tempering the mitigation efforts that aim to help these very marginalized groups.

To bridge these gaps, this paper leverages an extensive dataset of over 6 million comments from the online communities of 174 U.S. colleges on Reddit to examine the online dimension of hateful speech in college communities, addressing two research questions:

RQ1: How prevalent is hateful speech in online college communities, across the demographic categories such as gender, religion, race?

RQ2: How does exposure to online hate affect an individual’s expression of their psychological state on social media, particularly stress?

Our work operationalizes hateful speech in online college communities on the hateful content posted in these subreddits. We devise College Hate Index (CHX) to quantify the manifestation of hateful speech across various target categories of hate in an online college community. Our findings suggest that, despite several existing moderation policies on college subreddits [10], hateful speech remains prevalent, and is actually 25% more than that in non-college subreddit communities (Figure 1). Adopting a causal inference framework [28, 29], we then find that an individual’s exposure to online hateful speech impacts their online stress expression (see Figure 2 and Table 1). In fact, when exposed to hate, these individuals show a wide range of stress levels, which we characterize using a grounded construct of psychological endurance to hate. Individuals with lower endurance tend to show greater emotional vulnerability, and neuroticism, and conscientiousness traits.

Although this work does not capture offline hateful speech on college campuses, it advances the body of research in *online* hateful speech by examining it in a hitherto under-explored community – college campuses, and by surfacing its psychological effects – a hitherto under-explored research direction. We discuss the implications of our work in providing an important empirical dimension to the

Figure 2: a) Cohen’s d for evaluating matching balance of covariates of activity features and baseline (B.) stress and hate exposure; b) Kernel Density Estimation of user distribution with change in stress expression.

Table 1: Regression coefficients for hate categories and change in stress expression (*) $p < 0.001$.**

Category	Coefficient
Behavior***	2.6×10^{-4}
Class***	5.1×10^{-4}
Disability***	7.3×10^{-3}
Ethnicity***	3.9×10^{-3}
Gender***	8.1×10^{-3}
Physical***	1.5×10^{-3}
Race***	1.7×10^{-3}
Religion***	1.3×10^{-5}
Sexual Ort.***	5.7×10^{-3}
Other***	1.5×10^{-3}

college speech debate, and for supporting policy-making and well-being support and intervention efforts to tackle the psychological effects of *online* hateful speech in college communities.

Privacy, Ethics, and Disclosure. Given the sensitive nature of our study, despite working with public de-identified data from Reddit, we do not report any information that associates hateful speech and its psychological effects with specific individuals or college campuses. To describe our approach and to ground our research better, this paper includes paraphrased and partially masked excerpts of hateful comments, for which we suggest caution to readers.

2 IMPLICATIONS

2.1 Socio-Political and Policy Implications

The speech debate has been a part of the American socio-political discussions for many years now [16]. In particular, on college campuses, it presents many complexities in decision or policy making that seeks to combat hateful speech within campuses [12]. While this paper does not provide any resolution to this debate, it makes empirical, objective, and data-driven contributions and draws valuable insights towards an informed discussion on this topic.

First, while the speech debate so far has largely focused in the *offline* context, as our study shows, hateful speech in the *online* domain also bears negative impacts on the exposed population, especially in situated communities like college campuses. Our findings align with prior work on the psychological impacts on hateful speech in the offline context [17, 33]. At the same time, they extend the literature by showing that there are not only pronounced differences in the prevalence of various hate speech types, but also the exposure to hate affects individuals’ online stress expression [26]. Here we note that antisocial behaviors like hateful speech continue to be a pressing issue for online communities [6, 7], but the effects of online hateful speech remains the subject of little empirical research. Thus, these findings help to account for a previously under-explored, but a critical facet of the speech debate, especially in the context of college campuses.

Second, our findings add new dimensions to the college speech debate centering around legal, ownership, and governance issues. These issues involve not only those who trigger and those who

are exposed to online hateful speech, but also the owners, the moderators, the users, and the creators of social media platforms, who may not necessarily be part of the college community.

Third, our work highlights a new policy challenge: how to decipher when online and offline hateful speech reinforce each other, and to delineate their psychological effects, particularly in a situated community where there is likely overlap between the online and offline social worlds. Our work indicates that the affordances of social media, such as anonymity and low effort information sharing amplify the complexities of the speech debate on college campuses. Typically, colleges can choose to restrict the time, place, and manner of someone's speech. However, when speech is not physically located on campus, these affordances can be exploited to quickly reach large segments of the campus population, posing new threats. Consequently, how should college stakeholders respond, when, based on our approach, a student is found to use online hate, observably outside of the physical setting of the campus, targeting a person of marginalized identity?

Finally, our work opens up discussions about the place of "counter-speech" in these communities to undermine the psychological effects of hate, alongside accounting for the legal concerns and governance challenges that enforcing certain community norms may pose [25]. We do note that any such discussions promoting counter speech would need to factor in the general etiquette of conduct expected from the members of the college community to avoid misethnic or chauvinistic phrasing, and to maintain a vibrant and inclusive environment which is respectful of other members [13].

2.2 Technological Implications

An important contribution of our work is the novel computational framework we developed to assess the pervasiveness and the psychological effects of online hateful speech on the members of online college communities. We believe these methods can lead to two types of technology implications:

2.2.1 Mental Health Support Provisions on College Campuses. The ease of interpretation and the ability to track language changes over time allows our empirical measure of online hateful speech in college campuses to be robust and generalizable across different online college communities, and also accessible to various stakeholders, unlike what is supported by existing hate speech detection techniques [31]. Our methods can thus be leveraged by college authorities to make informed decisions surrounding the speech dilemma on campuses, promote civil online discourse among students, and employ timely interventions when deemed appropriate. While our approach to assess the prevalence of hateful speech is likely to be not perfectly accurate, alongside human involvement in validating these outcomes, timely interventions to reduce the harmful effects of online hateful language can be deployed. As Olteanu et al. [21] recently pointed out that exogenous events can lead to online hatefulness, our framework can assist to proactively detect the psychological ramifications of online hate at their nascent stage to prevent negative outcomes.

Additionally, our work helps us draw insights about the attributes of individuals with higher vulnerability and lower psychological endurance to online hateful speech. This can assist in instrumenting tailored and timely support efforts, and evidence-based

decision strategies on campuses. We further note that, any form of hateful speech, whether online or offline, elicits both problem- and emotion- focused coping strategies, and the victims of hateful speech seek support [15]. Many colleges already provide various self, peer, and expert-help resources to cater to vulnerable students. These efforts may be aligned to also consider the effects of *online* hateful speech exposure as revealed in our work.

2.2.2 Moderation Efforts in Online College Communities. Our findings suggest that hateful speech *does* prevail in college subreddits. However, unlike most other online communities, banning or extensively censoring content on college subreddits—a strategy widely adopted today [6, 19] as a measure to counter online antisocial behavior can have counter-effects. Such practices would potentially preclude students from accessing an open discussion board with their peers where not only many helpful information is shared, but also which enables them to socialize and seek support around academic and personal life related topics. Rather, our work can be considered to be a "call-to-action" for the moderators to adopt measures that go beyond blanket banning or censorship. For instance, our approach to assess the stress and hate exposure of users can assist moderators to tune community environment and adapt norms in a way that discourages hateful speech [27]. This could be subreddit guidelines that outline moderation strategies not only discouraging offensive and unwelcoming content, but also around content that *affects* community members. For example, the subreddit *r/lifeprotips* explicitly calls out against "*tips or comments that encourage behavior that can cause injury or harm to others can cause for a (user) ban*". Other moderation strategies can also be adopted: such as using labels in specific posts which are perturbing, along the lines of *r/AskReddit* which uses "[Serious]" to particularly label very important and relevant discussion threads.

Moderators can also provide assistance and support via peer-matching, and include pointers to external online help resources, especially to members who are vulnerable to the negative psychological impacts of online hateful content. Complementarily, as argued in recent research [4], making the harmful effects of hateful language transparent to the community members in carefully planned and strategic manner, could curb the prevalence of antisocial practices including hateful speech. Specifically in online college communities, where the members are geographically situated and embedded in their offline social ties [3, 8], knowledge of the negative psychological repercussion of certain online practices could influence them to refrain from or not engage with such behaviors.

In the offline context, the college speech debate has also aroused discussions surrounding *safe spaces*: particular sites of campuses where students join peers, and *trigger warnings*: explicit statements that certain material discussed in an academic environment might upset sensitive students [13, 34]. These measures are advocated to help in minimize hateful speech and its effects. We argue that analogous measures are possible in online communities as well, using the design affordances of the social media platforms (e.g., creating separate subreddits for minority communities in a college, or providing pop-up warnings on certain posts). However, both safe spaces and trigger warnings are critiqued as they are exclusionary

and are harmful for open discourse in colleges. So, any such possible consequences should also be carefully evaluated before such measures are adopted in online communities of college students.

2.3 Ethical Implications

Amid the controversy surrounding the freedom of expression, defining (online) hateful speech remains a complex subject of ethical, legal, and administrative interest, especially on college campuses that are known to value inclusiveness in communities, and to facilitate progressive social exchange. While our definition of hateful speech in online college communities may not be universal, our measurement approach provides an objective understanding of the dynamics and impacts of hateful environment within online college communities. Nevertheless, any decision and policy making based on our findings requires careful and in-depth supplemental ethical analysis, beyond the empirical analysis we present in this paper. For instance, to what extent online hateful speech infringes on the speech provisions on specific campuses remains a topic that needs careful evaluation. Importantly, supported by our analysis, campus stakeholders must navigate a two-prong ethical dilemma: one around engaging with those who use online hateful speech, and two, around treating its extreme manifestations, like hate related threats and altercations directed at campus community members, or its interference with the institution's educational goals.

We finally caution against our work being perceived as a means to facilitate surveillance of student speech on college campuses, or as a guideline to censor speech on campus. Our work is not intended to be used to intentionally or inadvertently marginalize or influence prejudice against those groups who are already marginalized (by gender, race, religion, sexual orientation etc.), or vulnerable, and are often the targets of hateful speech on campuses.

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